

The Value and Advantages of Artificial Intelligence in Foreign Language Teaching

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Abstract: *This article provides information about what artificial intelligence is, what are its advantages, its role in our life and its help in science. The debate about artificial intelligence has been going on for almost 50 years. Experts have not yet come to a conclusion. Some worry that mass unemployment could rise as a result of their increasing popularity. Another group of experts insists that artificial intelligence should be treated positively.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, foreign language, computers, best solution, deep learning, business decisions, mass unemployment, positive attitude.*

Introduction:

Artificial intelligence is a special field of computer science, which deals with the creation of computer systems with capabilities usually associated with the human mind: language understanding, teaching, discussion, problem solving, translation, and similar capabilities. Currently, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms and software systems designed to perform various actions, and it can cope with a number of tasks that the human mind can perform.

At this point, we found it necessary to dwell on how the concept of artificial intelligence appeared. The term artificial intelligence was introduced by John McCarthy in 1955. In 1956, McCarthy and others organized the Dartmouth Summer Research Project Conference on Artificial Intelligence. This initiative has led to many inventions such as machine learning, deep learning, and predictive analytics. In addition, this initiative gave rise to a new field - data science. In the 1990s, a new page was opened in the development of artificial intelligence. In 1997, an IBM computer named Deep Blue became the first computer in history to beat world chess champion Garry Kasparov.

Artificial intelligence is based on imitating human cognitive processes through creation and application of speech in different languages in a rapid learning environment. Simply put, artificial intelligence is a technology that guides computers to think and solve like humans. To achieve this goal, three main components are required: systems (high-powered computers); big data and skills in their management; SI algorithms (software code); The closer artificial intelligence is to human intelligence, the more data and computing resources are required to create it.

Method and material:

Today, the concept of artificial intelligence is very common, for example, programs on your mobile device: Google, Yandex, Chat GPT, lingvo dictionaries, various games, etc. are also clear examples of artificial intelligence. .

Only their coverage is smaller and they can only help you in a certain direction. That is, depending on the type of actions you want to perform, you use the appropriate program.

Today, the volume of new information generated by humans and machines in foreign language learning far exceeds the ability of humans to absorb, interpret, and make complex decisions. And artificial intelligence is able to find and analyze a large amount of data and accept new tasks based on them.

For example, in the "new words and phrases" game, most people know how to win. But not everyone knows that there are countless unique new expressions in this game, and some of them end with synonyms and explanations. When searching for a certain word, the device also gives a synonym, antonym, and a number of explanations for the new word. ChatGPT is a conversational AI model developed by OpenAI, based on the GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) architecture. It's designed to understand and generate human-like text based on the input it receives:

- **Data:** ChatGPT is trained on a vast amount of text data from the internet, including books, articles, websites, and more. This data helps the model learn patterns in language, grammar, facts, and some level of reasoning.
- **Pre-training and Fine-tuning:** The model undergoes pre-training on large datasets to learn general language features. Then, it can be fine-tuned with specific datasets and instructions to improve performance on particular tasks, like answering questions or holding conversations.
- **Conversational Skills:** ChatGPT can engage in conversations on a wide range of topics, from casual chat to more specialized subjects. It can answer questions, provide explanations, offer advice, and generate creative content.
- **Language Understanding:** The model can understand and generate text in multiple languages, though it performs best in English.
- **Contextual Awareness:** ChatGPT can maintain context over multiple turns in a conversation, allowing it to provide more coherent and relevant responses.
- **Customer Support:** Businesses use ChatGPT for automated customer support, answering common queries, and assisting customers with various tasks.
- **Content Creation:** Writers, marketers, and other content creators use it to generate ideas, write drafts, and even produce full articles.
- **Education:** Students and educators use ChatGPT for tutoring, explaining complex topics, and providing study help.
- **Entertainment:** It can be used for casual conversation, storytelling, and other creative pursuits.

Computers are extremely efficient at performing these combinations and actions and finding the best solution. Artificial intelligence, its development and deep learning is the future of business decision-making. In the future, this technology can create an opportunity to find the right solution in all areas of the economy. The debate about artificial intelligence has been going on for almost 50 years. Experts have not yet come to a conclusion. Some worry that mass unemployment could rise as a result of their increasing popularity. Another group of experts insists that artificial intelligence should be treated positively.

Even among IT billionaires, there are differences of opinion. In particular, the founder of SpaceX, Elon Musk, believes that artificial intelligence can threaten human civilization. According to Musk, artificial intelligence will cause massive labor problems. The reason is that robots can do everything better than us. In the pursuit of cutting-edge technology, companies can lose sight of the dangers posed by artificial intelligence. Also, the head of Microsoft, Bill Gates, touches on its harm: "In a few decades, when robots start to do most of the work, artificial intelligence will become so powerful that

it will eventually start to worry us." . At this point, it is worth noting that many prestigious higher education institutions of the world are effectively using artificial intelligence training in language learning.

Result and discussion:

Today, in some countries, the use of robot-nurses, driverless vehicles, and the service of drones delivering orders has been established. Even in the IELTS, lingvoSkill and Tesol test systems that determine the level of language proficiency, special robots are performing some of the tasks of the employees. Using ChatGPT to learn a foreign language offers several advantages, making it a valuable tool for language learners:

- **Conversational Practice:** ChatGPT allows you to engage in real-time conversations in the language you're learning, helping you practice sentence construction, vocabulary, and grammar in a dynamic way.
- **Immediate Feedback:** You can get instant corrections or suggestions on your language use, allowing you to learn from mistakes and improve your proficiency more quickly.
- **Tailored Content:** ChatGPT can adjust the complexity of the conversation based on your proficiency level, offering simpler sentences for beginners or more complex discussions for advanced learners.
- **Focus on Specific Areas:** You can target specific language skills, such as grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, or cultural context, depending on your learning needs.
- **24/7 Access:** Unlike traditional tutors, ChatGPT is available anytime, providing flexible learning opportunities that fit your schedule.
- **No Geographic Barriers:** You can practice languages that might be hard to find native speakers for in your local area, such as less commonly taught languages.
- **Variety of Topics:** ChatGPT can discuss a wide range of topics, helping you learn vocabulary relevant to different contexts, from everyday conversation to specialized subjects like business or travel.
- **Role-playing Scenarios:** You can simulate real-world interactions, such as ordering food at a restaurant, asking for directions, or negotiating in a business meeting, which helps build practical language skills.
- **Contextual Understanding:** ChatGPT can provide explanations about cultural nuances, idioms, and customs associated with the language, giving you a deeper understanding beyond just vocabulary and grammar.
- **Exposure to Varieties of the Language:** You can explore different dialects, slang, and regional expressions, which are often crucial for sounding more natural in the language.
- **Interactive and Fun:** The conversational nature of ChatGPT makes language learning more engaging and less monotonous than traditional study methods like rote memorization.
- **Creative Exercises:** You can ask ChatGPT to generate language games, quizzes, or storytelling exercises that make learning more enjoyable.
- **Cost-effective:** Compared to hiring a tutor or purchasing language learning software, ChatGPT offers a relatively low-cost or even free option for practicing and improving your language skills.
- **Supplement to Other Resources:** It can complement other language learning methods, such as textbooks, apps, and classes, providing a well-rounded approach to mastering a foreign language.

- No Judgment: For learners who feel shy or self-conscious about making mistakes, practicing with ChatGPT offers a judgment-free environment where you can practice as much as needed without feeling pressured.
- Self-paced Learning: You can learn at your own pace, spending as much time as you need on difficult concepts without the pressure of keeping up with a class or tutor.
- Repetition: If you need to go over certain phrases or concepts multiple times, ChatGPT will patiently repeat and explain as often as necessary.
- Multilingual Capabilities: ChatGPT supports a wide range of languages, allowing you to switch between languages or even practice multiple languages in the same session.

Scientists are trying to make their appearance and voice as human as possible. Many may lose their jobs because of this. It is said that unemployment can threaten teachers, medical workers, treasurers, postal workers, accountants and office workers. Artificial intelligence can easily perform their tasks. Despite all the objections and criticisms, artificial intelligence does not stop developing and helping people. Its importance is growing, especially in the comparative teaching of languages.

For example: If we take the verb take, it is shortened in dictionary books only in the form of "take" (verb). In Uzbek, the word "take" can be translated as "olmoq." For example, "to take a book" would be "to take a book."

It is given in the sentence as "I decided to take a walk in the park to clear my mind", while Chat GPT uses artificial intelligence. The verb "take" has several meanings depending on the context.

1. To acquire possession of something: To get or receive something, such as "to take a book from the shelf."
2. To capture or seize: To physically grab or hold onto something, such as "to take someone's hand."
3. To accept or agree to do something: For example, "to take a job" or "to take responsibility."
4. To consume or ingest: To eat or drink something, such as "to take medicine."
5. To require or necessitate: Used to indicate the need for something, such as "This task will take time." The specific meaning depends on the usage in a sentence.

Now, robots are able to create relatively complex words and analyze them. The unique collaboration between robotic linguists and automated teachers has greatly increased efficiency. If we look for phrases using artificial intelligence, we can see the following:

1. Take it easy: To relax or not stress about something. - Example: "You've been working hard all day; it's time to take it easy."
2. Take the plunge: To commit to a risky or uncertain course of action. - Example: "After years of planning, they finally took the plunge and started their own business."
3. Take with a grain of salt: To view something skeptically or not take it too seriously. - Example: "You should take his advice with a grain of salt; he's known for exaggerating."
4. Take the bull by the horns: To confront a difficult situation head-on. - Example: "It's time to take the bull by the horns and address the issue directly."
5. Take a back seat: To allow someone else to be in control or to play a less prominent role. - Example: "She decided to take a back seat and let her team members lead the project."
6. Take the wind out of someone's sails: To deflate someone's enthusiasm or confidence. - Example: "Her harsh criticism really took the wind out of his sails."

7. Take five: To take a short break, typically five minutes. - Example: "Let's take five before we continue with the meeting."
8. Take it or leave it: An offer that is non-negotiable. - Example: "That's my final price - take it or leave it."
9. Take the cake: To be the most outstanding in a negative way. - Example: "I've heard some excuses before, but that one really takes the cake."
10. Take the heat: To endure criticism or pressure. - Example: "As the leader, you'll have to take the heat when things go wrong."

Conclusion:

The article discussed the society of artificial intelligence and how it began to take its place in science, foreign language teaching, entertainment and many other fields. Artificial intelligence will have very low "labor" costs, so we can use it for free or at very low cost. In the development of science, Google, Googlebooks, Yandex, Duolingo, Chat GPT, and other words, the widespread introduction of advanced artificial intelligence technologies will improve the quality of the rapidly growing potential of the world's population, and various services will be repeatedly will improve. Most likely, it can bring people closer to the well-being of their lives.

REFERENCES

1. Russell, Stuart J.; Norvig, Peter. *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*, 4th, Hoboken: Pearson, 2021. ISBN 978-0-13-461099-3.
2. McCorduck, Pamela (2004), *Machines Who Think* (2nd-nashr), Natick, MA: A. K. Peters, Ltd., ISBN 1-56881-205-1
3. NRC (United States National Research Council) *Developments in Artificial Intelligence,. Funding a Revolution: Government Support for Computing Research*. National Academy Press, 1999.
4. McCarthy, John; Minsky, Marvin; Rochester, Nathan; Shannon, Claude A *Proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence* (1955).
5. Toews, Rob. *Transformers Revolutionized AI. What Will Replace Them?.* Forbes (2023y).
6. Goldman, Sharon. *10 years later, deep learning 'revolution' rages on, say AI pioneers Hinton, LeCun and Li* VentureBeat (2022 y)
7. *Ask the AI experts: What's driving today's progress in AI? .* McKinsey & Company. (2018 y).
8. Frank, Michael *US Leadership in Artificial Intelligence Can Shape the 21st Century Global Order* (en-US). *The Diplomat* (2023. 22.09).
9. "Artificial Intelligence: A Guide for Thinking Humans" by Melanie Mitchell
10. "Human Compatible: Artificial Intelligence and the Problem of Control" by Stuart Russell.
11. ABIDOVA, Z. (2024). INTERPRETATION OF VERBS OF THOUGHT IN ENGLISH ANNOTATED DICTIONARIES. *News of the NUUZ*, 1(1.5.2), 239-284. <https://doi.org/10.69617/nuuz.v1i1.5.2.4266>
12. Babayeva, Komila Rishatovna , & Istamova, Gulnoza Utkurovna (2023). PRAGMATIC PROBLEMS THAT ARISE IN UZBEK GROUPS IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3 (2), 418-425.

13. Komila Rishatovna Babayeva, & Gulnoza Utkurovna Istamova. (2020). Preservation Of The Originality Of The Work Of Art In Translation .
14. Norov Toji Omonovich, Aliyev Bekdavlat, Khodjakhanov Muzaffar Mukhtarovich, Bayaliev Djakhongir Kaynarbekovich, Darmonov Aliyorjon Abdukhalilovich, & Babayeva Komila Rishatovna. (2020). HUMAN AND HUMANITARIAN IDEAS IN THE PHILOSOPHY OF ALISHER NAVOI. PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology, 17(7), 5470-5476. Retrieved from <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/2710>